

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

TRANSPARENT PROCESSES FOR “SMART COLLABORATION” IN THE MOUNTAIN REGION [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 13

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1. Introduction

The focus of Spoke 4 Smartwest flagship project is on contrasting depopulation in the mountain regions. Since the regeneration of mountain areas and villages requires a complex interplay of economic, social, and environmental factors (Grecchi et al. 2025), we believe that fostering social innovation is a cornerstone of all efforts with this aim and that networks of co-working spaces are instrumental to this aim. By social innovation, we mean “new social practices that aim to meet social needs in a better way than the existing solutions, resulting from - for example - working conditions, education, community development or health” (Schwarz 2010).

Figure 1 - Overview of the work

Figure 1 provides an overall glance of the main concepts that are involved in the research work. As can be seen, the core instrument that we foresee as fundamental for enabling social innovation in the mountain areas is the development of a set of co-working spaces, to be organized in a network. Such places provide attractive features not only for the residents, whose home might not provide adequate working spaces, but also for foreign workers and companies which might be interested in delocating (for some time) their working activities to an area that provides both adequate services (e.g. office spaces, meeting rooms, internet connection) and the benefits of being out of town, in the quiet of nature. Trivially, a co-working space is a place where meeting others is facilitated by the very nature of the place itself. To be truly attractive, especially in the long term, the location of the co-working space must offer attractive features that generally vary depending on the type of user. For instance, locals might find it attractive to be close to schools.

Smart collaborations can be either internal to a company, and involve persons with different competences who collaborate on a project and are displaced to a co-working space to support such collaboration, or external, and involve freelancers or professionals, working for different companies, who join to give birth to new initiatives. In both cases, co-working spaces come at hand. Concerning depopulation, co-working is an incentive for people to live and work in the mountain territory. In particular, it is expected to overcome some of the limitations that affect remote working, like bad impacts on personal life-work balance, lack of motivation, and such like (Risi and Pronzato, 2021). On the other hand, smart collaboration heavily relies on digital artifacts, like shared notes, tasks, and business processes, as well as digital tools, ranging from remote conferencing systems to cloud services and process management systems. These are all fundamental assets and play an extremely important role. Before describing the demonstrators, we introduce the main concepts.

1.1 Smart collaboration

Smart collaboration is defined as the integration of individual, specialized expertise of knowledge workers to deliver high-quality, customized solutions on complex issues (Gardner, 2016), in opposition to a more traditional organization of work, where a company is structured vertically into specialized silos. In this deliverable, we extend the term to cover any kind of work, i.e., not necessarily restricted to knowledge workers, and we consider it under the scope of NODES - SMARWEST, that is, the promotion of digital technologies for improving the performance and sustainability of companies that are located in mountain areas.

In most cases, smart collaboration relies on forms of remote working (a key focus of this deliverable), and on the technological infrastructure and tools that support it. The use of technology allows smart collaboration to be distributed in different ways: competencies may be distributed between different actors; actors may be geographically distributed, and may work for different institutions or be freelancers; the collaboration may happen in places that are different each time and that may be different from an organization working office; collaborations may vary each time in its implementation and actors involved. As one can see, a smart collaboration has a distributed and dynamic nature by definition.

Research shows that smart collaboration delivers significant financial and people-related benefits to organizations, such as higher profit margins, greater customer loyalty, talent attraction and retention, and competitive advantage when specialists collaborate across functional boundaries (Burgens-Pas and Seckler, 2022). Bringing together their distinct expertise and knowledge, specialists may also create entirely new types of services that can attract new clients. Of course, such collaborations require trust among the parties, both in the sense of respect for each other's competence and in the sense of belief in each other's integrity.¹

Smart collaboration, in our perspective, concerns the processes that occur inside a company as well as the creation of double networks (Malecki, 2011), that is, the creation of networks that are external to the company and that aim at capturing ideas and profit from innovative initiatives that emerge in the outside world. This is also particularly interesting for individual workers who work as freelancers, who would like to expand their activities beyond their usual channels.

¹ Da <https://clp.law.harvard.edu/research/research-projects/teamwork-and-collaboration/> Teamwork and Collaboration, Heidi K. Gardner.

In the project, we focused on the implications of exploiting the so-called “weak ties” that connect the patrons of co-working spaces. We are interested in smart collaborations that arise spontaneously, that is, without being strictly imposed by a controlling entity (an organization), but rather involve persons because of their competencies and needs. As one can see, smart collaborations are, by their nature, dynamic and emergent. The claim is that positioning co-working spaces in a suitable way in the mountain regions may be a driver to reduce depopulation and foster innovation.

1.2 Co-working spaces

Co-working spaces are imposing themselves as a consequence of the transformations the world of work has undergone in the last ten years, with an increasing emphasis on flexibility and collaboration (Bouncken et al, 2020), which has led to the rise of the remote working model and of hybrid work models. Such models mix remote working with traditional in-office activities, reshaping the working landscape and gaining widespread popularity. These spaces, designed for shared use by individual workers or small businesses, have proliferated globally. Many co-working spaces are located in large urban areas, near clients –usually highly skilled ICT professionals, freelancers, and creative-class employees (Marino et al., 2023; Grazian, 2020; Mariotti et al., 2023; Belk, 2014). The scarce opportunities for collaboration and innovation between professionals and local businesses, and the difficulty of finding networking and professional growth opportunities, which are typically associated with small, remote communities, are seen as disadvantages. In order to overcome these disadvantages, we study a different model: co-working spaces are re-imagined as interlinked hubs, that are situated in small villages, and designed not only to foster the traditional co-working model –such as shared resources and communal working environments- but also to serve as focal points for skill retention, attraction, and sharing, providing an infrastructure that fosters smart collaboration. We call such an organization a Network of Co-working Spaces (NCS).

As its name suggests, an NCS is a structure that connects many co-working spaces, linking them according to their geographic proximity, and helping specialized “districts” to emerge. More in detail, an NCS has three main characteristics:

- It helps users to find co-working spaces.
- It is meant to be managed and supported by a community – indeed, we expect the NCS to be managed by local (public) mountain/rural communities or organizations.
- It supports the emergence of structured networks of competence districts.

The latter point results from the observation that, by establishing these networks around core regional competencies and thematic areas, NCSs encourage residents to engage deeply with their fields while also attracting external talents, who look for specialized collaborative communities. This structure emphasizes local governance, ensuring that the initiatives align closely with regional development goals and that they are integrated into the local socioeconomic fabric. The co-working hubs are no longer merely seen as places of work, but as active centers that foster smart collaborations and entrepreneurial activity. This model leverages the dynamics of shared economies and resource pooling, potentially leading to the birth of new startups, driving local employment, and contributing to a robust and resilient regional economy.

Smart collaborations and remote working are parts of a same vision, as can be understood by considering the so-called pillars of remote working, that are:

1. Flexibility: employees and freelancers work where they want, as long as they meet deadlines and objectives.
2. Technology: technologies are an essential asset that links geographically dispersed teams. Some examples are: online collaboration tools, project management systems, virtual conferencing systems, and instant messaging.
3. Focus on results: the focus is more on achievements than on hours worked. Workers are more autonomous in the organization of the activities, and they are encouraged to be responsible.
4. Well-being and productivity: flexibility provided by remote work helps workers to better balance between their job and the constraints of everyday life.

Flexibility allows workers to explore by interacting with the other patrons of a co-working space. The same technology that supports team collaboration supports the implementation of new collaborations. Focus on results in this case is the driver: in the case of smart collaborations the focus will be on new or better results. Well-being and productivity come as a by-product because, at its core, the organizational model is that of hybrid work.

1.3 Processes

The term business process (or simply process, in this document) is used to identify a set of activities that are performed by a group of individuals in coordination in an organizational and technical environment (Dumas et al, 2018). In certain cases, processes are well-formalized and workers are required to strictly adhere to them, but more often is the case, especially with micro, small, and medium enterprises, that processes exist as best practices or as habits, and are part of the company lore. Thus, they cannot be easily shared or analysed, for instance, to implement improvements.

The activities that are part of a business process jointly aim at realizing a business goal. A business process is enacted within a company, but the company may interact with other companies by playing roles in some business processes of other organizations (consider, for instance, a supply chain where a company acts as a client of another that acts as a supplier to the former).

Thus, the main features of a business process are: 1) it serves as a coordination medium between actors of the same organization and, potentially, with external collaborators (e.g., customers, suppliers, contractors, freelancers); 2) a process is designed to achieve a business goal (e.g., order management, loan application evaluation); and 3) a process is specified from the point of view of a single organization that is expected to enact it, and that has the control on the way its internal activities are performed, for instance, to meet certain standards. However, a business process may involve other organizations playing specific roles (e.g., think of a supply chain, with suppliers

being external companies. In this case, we will talk about cross-organizational business processes. Coordination with external parties is realized through communications (e.g., document/message exchange), often mediated by technology (e.g., messaging, email, forms, IOT solutions).

Interestingly, business processes can be designed and their executions can be monitored and analysed automatically in order to understand their adequacy and their effectiveness. Many tools on the market allow companies to support their activities by exploiting the power of business processes.

In the context of smart collaborations, business processes must be handled in a different way with respect to what is done traditionally. This is due to the need to take into account aspects that are more typical of remote working, where control over the worker is softer and execution is more oriented towards goal achievement. We relate, nevertheless, our work to the standard business process lifecycle that is used for managing processes inside a traditional organization, underlining the differences between the work that was carried out in the project and the traditional approach.

1.4 Demonstrators

This deliverable provides a set of demonstrators of tools that can be applied to foster smart collaboration:

1. NCS impact: the demonstrator² consists of a repast-symphony (Repast-symphony) agent-based simulation that takes as inputs population distributions in geographic areas, and geographic maps and computes, based on a set of formulas, the impact of the collocation of a set of co-working spaces in terms of likelihood of new collaborations, change in population number, change of pollution levels due to reduced car traffic. The simulation, whose code can be found here https://github.com/Andrea-s99/Coworking_Building_Simulation.git, uses high-quality geographic data about the Aosta Valley. The demonstrator's aim is to prove the feasibility of decision-support systems that can help investors, decision and policy makers in estimating the socio-economic return of possible investments. It also shows the potential of existing tools that can combine geographic data and resources in order to tailor simulations to specific areas, taking into account actual locations and roads.
2. model of co-working spaces: the aim of the demonstrator is to show the application of game theory to address the complexity of co-working networks, as tools/environments that create value by helping people who use them to create new collaborations, and thus increase the range of projects they are involved in.
3. Conformance checking extended with responsibilities. The demonstrator shows how classical techniques for conformance checking can be extended to account for additional information. The demonstrator shows how taking into account information in the form of responsibilities supports a better interpretation of the comparison of real execution with process models.
4. Process mining to support process analysis. The ultimate goal of process mining and business process management techniques is to analyse and improve the process and its representation in a company. We demonstrate the use of these techniques presenting the results of a collaboration of an IT company. We also present a set of guidelines that we developed to replicate the analysis process.

² The simulator was developed by Andrea Saraceni, in his thesis work, presented on April 1st, 2025.

We present the demonstrators by tying them, as much as possible, to the standard five phases of business process management (Dumas et al, 2018), namely: 1) design, 2) modelling, 3) execution, 4) monitoring, 5) improve.

Such phases are arranged in a lifecycle (see Figure 2) that accounts for the ideal management of the processes by which a company works and that should undergo constant revisions, e.g., to improve performance, to account for new cases, and to guarantee compliance with regulations.

Figure 2. Business process Lifecycle.

2. Execute

In order to decide whether to create a new co-working space or a new network of co-working spaces, it is important to foresee several aspects that concern the impact it may have both on the environment in which the new space will be introduced and on smart collaborations. Among these, the impact on the transport infrastructure of people moving from/to the place, CO2 emissions, and such like. Also, the impact on pre-existing co-working spaces could in principle be estimated.

To do this, we describe a simulation tool that was developed during NODES. Simulation is a well-known technique that is also part of the traditional approach of process management. It consists of the identification of several KPIs of interest (such as idle time, costs, and such like) on the definition of a process, and on parameters such as the rate of new instance creation, the average time for activity executions, and so on. Changes in the parameters have an impact on the KPIs. The variations can be assessed using simulations, which support the process of decision making.

Specifically, we show how the Repast Symphony tool (repast-simphony) can be configured and used for simulating a Network of Co-working Spaces (NCS), and analyze its impact on smart collaborations, on the geographical area, and on the workers' satisfaction.

2.1 Multiagent simulation

Repast Symphony, Recursive Porous Agent Simulation Toolkit (repast-simphony), is a toolkit that serves various purposes: it is an agent-based social simulation toolkit (ABSS), a modeling toolkit, and a cross-platform Java-based modeling system. Repast Symphony has been successfully applied in various application domains, including social sciences, consumer products, supply chains, manufacturing, epidemiology, biomedical systems modeling, and ancient pedestrian traffic.

Agent-Based Social Simulation (ABSS) represents the elements of a social system through artificial agents of different scales, placing them within a computer-simulated society to observe their behavior. By analyzing the data, researchers can verify hypotheses and understand emergent behavior, in order to apply these insights to real-world social systems. ABSS integrates three key fields: agent-based computing, social sciences, and computer simulation. Agent-based computing involves designing models and agents, while computer simulation focuses on executing the simulations and analyzing the results. Social sciences contribute theories and concepts that shape the model, enabling the study of social phenomena.

An agent is an abstraction that may represent any system, taking decisions and showing a behavior. It is situated in an environment that it can perceive by means of sensors and on which it can act by means of actuators. Concretely, in Repast agents are implemented as Java classes including variables and properties. The latter define the agent's behaviour, in terms of frequency and priority values. Such values are used by the Scheduler whenever it needs to determine which agent and which method to execute.

Icon	Description
	Coworking Building
	Workers' Office
	Coworker moving
	Coworker at work
	Service

Table 1. Icons that are associated with the elements of an NCS simulation.

2.2 NCS Simulation

The simulation was realized by Andrea Saraceni (Saraceni, 2025). It includes various elements, that are graphically represented by the icons in Table 1. Workers are implemented as agents, whose decisions are affected by the presence/absence of co-working spaces.

In order to design a simulation, it is necessary to define the factors that need to be computed by the simulation run. In the case of NCS several indicators could be thought of. We chose the following ones:

1. Reduction of worker commutes.

2. Influence on local population growth.
3. Income for local services.
4. CO2 emissions and fuel costs.
5. Level of satisfaction.
6. Opportunities for collaboration among coworkers.

The last directly concerns smart collaborations. The others concern both the environment (in a broad sense), that is the socio-geographical area in which the simulation is located, and the workers (satisfaction).

The NCS includes several co-working buildings which are located in various valleys of the Valle d'Aosta region. Thus, we simulate the choice that workers make, when they decide if going to a co-working space and, in this case, to which specific building. Concerning the geographical data, the simulation model relies on GIS-based technologies to locate the co-working buildings and the nearby services in the Valle d'Aosta region. It also allows us to model the pathways that workers follow in order to move to a coworking building. Thus, the simulation can compute traveling distances and CO2 emissions.

For the sake of simulation, we supposed that residents who may be interested in using a co-working space, live in some valley but work in Aosta, which is the only city in Valle d'Aosta or its surroundings. The distance and the wasted time are drivers that justify the choice of a co-working space, if available. Besides the city of Aosta, we considered the following towns:

- Saint-Rhémy,
- Cogne,
- Courmayeur,
- La Thuile,
- Champoluc,
- Buisson,
- Point-Saint-Martin,
- Grosseinay-Saint-Jean.

Each co-working building has a maximum capacity. So, when, during the simulation, the building turns out to be full, workers who would have chosen it will have to reach Aosta, that is, they will have to reach their default working office. As a simplification, we suppose that each city hosts at most one co-working building. Having more than one is surely possible in reality, but it did not contribute significantly to the aims of the demonstrator.

Figure 3. Geographic position of simulated services (yellow icons) with respect to Aosta. All geographical visualization exploit GIS data and the NASA World Wind library for an accurate and realistic rendering.

Services are distributed in the main towns of the considered valleys, as shown in Figure 3.

To model the agents' behaviour, we defined a set of predefined rules that account for the availability of working spaces in the co-working buildings, for the distances, and for interactions between workers.

The simulation can be run in two modalities:

- **Co-working not active:** this is the case when no co-working space is available, thus, workers move from home to the city of Aosta, where we imagine the worker's office to be. The simulation also considers the workers traveling back home at the end of the working day. Figure 4 represents this modality.
- **Co-working active:** In this modality, we simulate cases in which workers can decide to use co-working buildings. The co-working building where they move is simulated based on the availability of space, which is determined by the capacity of the co-working building and other coworkers present in the building. In case no space is available in the selected co-working building, the model simulates the worker moving to his/her office in Aosta.

Figure 5 represents this modality and Figure 6 shows that the simulation makes workers who commute follow actual roads, to increase accuracy and reliability of results.

Figure 4. Simulation scenario where coworking is disabled: all workers move to Aosta.

Figure 5. Simulation scenario where coworking is active. Left: location of the co-working buildings. Right: Saint-Rhémy valley and workers representation on the map.

Besides workers and co-working buildings, we also model services, such as restaurants, bars, shops, and such like. Each service is georeferenced, thus being associated with a position on the map and to a city in the region.

Figure 6. The screenshot shows an example of how the simulation makes workers who commute follow actual roads, to increase accuracy and reliability of results.

2.2.1 Computation of simulation estimates

CO2 emissions: When a worker moves either to his/her office in Aosta or to a co-working building, the simulation computes the CO2 emissions based on the distance the worker has to travel. Additionally, the system computes a cost that the worker has to pay to reach the destination. The cost depends on the distance, the vehicle type, its efficiency, and the traffic conditions. The fuel consumption is estimated based on the vehicle's average consumption and the distance. The cost is, thus, determined by multiplying the fuel consumption and the fuel cost. Similarly, the CO2 emissions are computed by multiplying the fuel consumption by the emission coefficient associated with the vehicle.

Worker Satisfaction Index. This index is a placeholder and could be substituted by more specialized measures. For demonstration purposes, the index considers the distance the worker has to travel (measured in terms of time spent to reach the destination) and the number of effective working hours. The resulting value is a percentage (range 0 - 100), where the higher the value, the higher the satisfaction because the worker was able to reduce the time spent commuting.

New collaborations. Workers can start new collaborations with other persons met within the co-working buildings. The creation of new collaborations is simulated by assigning a probability of collaboration between every pair of coworkers in the same co-working building, who do not have an ongoing collaboration between them. New collaborations contribute to increasing the economic value of a co-working building.

Collaboration index by valley. The collaboration index is also aggregated by valley. Within a valley, we consider the number of inhabitants and we model the impact on the request for co-working spaces in the co-working building of the valley or nearby valleys. Moreover, the presence

of co-working buildings in a valley contributes to the flourishing of services, and this is interpreted as an incentive for the population to remain in the valley.

Services' earnings. Finally, we compute the services' earnings as an economic index. The simulation is configured in such a way that when the coworking modality is active, the services' income is higher due to a higher number of clients. Vice versa, when the coworking modality is off, the income is still positive, but lower than in the previous case because it relies only on the local demand. Services can be of various types, like restaurant, shop, cafe.

The factors that we consider serve as a demonstration of the utility of a multiagent simulation. They are based on the distribution of the population in the valleys (obtained from public sources) and on the observation of real dynamics related to worker satisfaction and economic impacts of co-working. Of course, these factors can be adapted, or new ones can be considered. Identifying the most adequate set of factors requires the involvement of external persons such as domain experts, managers, or potential managers of coworking buildings in the area. This aspect is out of the scope of this deliverable, which is only aimed at demonstrating the potential of certain technologies.

2.2.2 Input parameters and estimate computation

The simulation provides results of a what-if analysis, that is aimed at evaluating different scenarios. In particular, the simulation considers two main scenarios: one with and the other without co-working spaces. The parameters that are monitored are:

- Increment/reduction of population: does the presence of a co-working space provide an incentive to live in a valley, thus promoting the growth of the local population and contributing to the development of the valley?
- Workers satisfaction: does the presence of a co-working building improve the workers' wellness by optimizing the trade-off between commuting time and working time?
- CO2 emissions and fuel costs: which is the environmental impact on the mobility model that is associated with commuting to go from home to the place of work and return?
- Services earnings: which is the impact on the earning of services that are present in the geographic area of a co-working space?
- New professional collaborations: to what extent does the presence of a co-working place impact on the birth of new synergies between the patrons of a co-working building? Does it facilitate working opportunities?

The parameters that can be configured in the simulation are described hereafter. In some cases, like coworker percentage, the value that was used is an educated guess.

- Rate percentage: This variable is used to modulate the growth or the change of some measures. It amounts to a percentage of variation that applies to the analysed phenomena. The default value is 10%.

- Coworking <city> activate: We define a boolean variable for each of the identified cities. True and False are used to represent the fact that the co-working building for the city is respectively active or inactive.
- Coworking <city> capacity: We define one such variable for each of the identified cities. It maintains the maximum capacity of the co-working building in a specific city.
- <city> Residents: Number of residents for each city. A value is provided for each town; for instance, Saint-Rhémy has 331 residents, while Point-Saint-Martin has 3541 residents.
- Coworker <city> Percentage: percentage of residents who decide to work in a co-working space. The default values vary depending on the town; for instance, 50% is the value for Saint-Rhémy, while 5% is the value set for Courmayeur.
- Time simulation: Integer number that defines the duration of the simulation in time units. The default is 10000 time units.
- Cost of fuel per liter. Double number. The default is 1.00.
- Min CO2 Emissions per liter: Minimum value of CO2 emissions per liter of fuel consumed. The default value is 1.5.
- Max CO2 Emissions per liter: Maximum value of CO2 emissions per liter of fuel consumed. The default value is 2.
- randomSeed: integer number, it is automatically generated to initialize the pseudo-random number generator.

The outcomes of the simulation are computed thanks to functions that we report. Note that the formulas constitute a module of the overall architecture of the simulation. Consequently, it is possible to change the formulas without changing the whole simulator. To compute the trend in population growth in the valleys, we defined the formula:

$$R_{t+1} = \sum_{t=1}^n R_t + \left(\frac{S}{100}\right) \cdot k \cdot rate$$

where:

- R_{t+1} is the number of residents at time $t + 1$ that we want to estimate.
- R_t is the estimated number of residents in the valley at time t .
- n is the duration of the simulation (number of ticks).
- S represents co-workers' satisfaction.
- k is a predefined growth index.
- $rate$ is a percentage estimate of the population growth. It is one of the input parameters of the simulation.

Concerning the coworker satisfaction, we compute it as follows:

$$S = \left(1 - \frac{T_t}{T_w * 60}\right) \cdot 100$$

where:

- S is the satisfaction index.
- T_t is the travel time for a coworker (in minutes)
- T_w is the number of worked hours for a coworker (in minutes).

The value T_w is computed based on a normal distribution and can assume a value in the range 4 - 8 hours.

One can observe that coworking (in the nearest co-working building) can reduce the travelling time, thus increasing the satisfaction index.

Similarly, it is possible to compute the CO2 emission and the economic cost for workers. Specifically, distance is measured along the route that workers follow to reach their destination, taking into account the available roads along the valleys. The number of kilometers, multiplied by the emission rate per kilometer, produces the overall CO2 emission per each journey. In the simulation, when a worker's position is less than predefined threshold, the work is considered as "arrived". Otherwise, he/she will continue to move towards the destination, adapting the position by way of small random variations to obtain a more realistic simulation. The economic cost paid by the worker along the itinerary depends on the distance travelled, on the kind of vehicle and its efficiency, besides exogenous factors like traffic. In general, however, the longer the distance the higher the cost. when computing such factors, we made a simplification consisting in using average fuel consumption. This and distance allow computing the vehicle fuel consumption, and the fuel cost allows then to compute the economic cost for the worker. The formulas that are used to calculate CO2 emissions and fuel costs are:

1. $El_{CO_2} = CO_{2\ min} + (random \cdot CO_{2\ max} - CO_{2\ min})$

2. $F_u = d \cdot F_c$

3. $C_{fuel} = F_u \cdot Cl_f$

4. $E_{CO_2} = F_u \cdot El_{CO_2}$

5. $C_{fuel,tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_{fuel,i} \cdot S_{p_i}$

6. $E_{CO_2,tot} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{CO_2,i} \cdot S_{p_i}$

where:

- n is the number of ticks used by the simulation,

- $random \sim U(0,1)$ is a random variable with uniform distribution between 0 and 1, and allows us to determine a random quantity in the specified range,
- $CO_{2\ min}$ is the minimum value for CO2 emissions per liter of fuel and it is a model input parameter,
- $CO_{2\ max}$ is the maximum value for CO2 emissions per liter of fuel and it is a model input parameter,
- d is the distance,
- F_c is fuel consumption in liters per kilometer,
- F_u is used fuel,
- Cl_f is the cost of fuel per liter, it is an input parameter of the model,
- C_{fuel} is the cost of fuel per single itinerary,
- El_{CO_2} is CO2 emission per liter of fuel,
- E_{CO_2} is the CO₂ emission per single itinerary,
- S_{p_i} is a flag that indicates whether a worker is moving in the considered moment: value is 0 if the worker is working, 1 if the worker is along his/her itinerary,
- $C_{fuel,tot}$ is the total cost of fuel,
- $E_{CO_2,tot}$ is the total emission of CO₂.

The first formula calculates CO2 emission by adding, to the minimal emission, a random variation. Other formulas are trivial, and allow calculating CO2 emissions and economic cost for fuel. Clearly, a worker who can rely on a closeby co-working space will do shorter itineraries and spend less for fuel. CO2 emissions will also be reduced.

Earning for local services is computed as follows.

$$h = X$$

$$E_{t_0} = 0$$

$$E_{t_{i+1}} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{t_i} + (h \cdot 0.50) + \sum_{i=1}^n E_{t_i} \cdot k \cdot rate^{1.5}$$

where:

- n is the number of ticks of the simulation,
- $X \sim U(4,8)$ is the working time, in hours, of a worker. It is a random variable with uniform distribution ranging between 4 and 8 hours,

- E_{t_i} is the actual earning at time i ,
- $E_{t_{i+1}}$ is the total earning at time $i+1$,
- h is the total number of working hours,
- k is a proportionality coefficient, set to $(3 \cdot 10^{-7})$,
- $rate$ is the estimate of earning growing, it is a parameter provided in input to the simulation model.

Earning depends on local services previous earning, on the total number of working hours by coworkers, and on a proportional coefficient that varies based on the parameter rate and represents an earning increment parameter. The formula is dynamic and different simulations will generally reflect the specific conditions of the run. Rate can be considered the estimate of the percentage of earning increase depending on the presence and the permanence of coworkers.

Concerning smart collaboration, we defined the following formula

$$C_{i+1} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i + I(N \geq 2 \wedge X \leq P_c)$$

where:

- C_{i+1} is the number of collaborations at time i .
- n is the time simulation value.
- P_c is the probability of collaboration ($0.8 = 80\%$),
- $X \sim U(0,1)$ is a random variable following a uniform distribution in the interval $[0,1]$,
- N is the number of coworkers.
- $I(X \leq P_c)$ is a function returning 1 if the number of coworkers is greater than or equal to 2, and if the condition $X \leq P_c$ is satisfied, returns 0 otherwise.
- C_i is the number of collaborations at time i .

Co-working spaces foster the creation of new professional and personal connections, creating a dynamic ecosystem where ideas, needs, competence, and resources can be shared, promoting innovation and professional growth. Collaborations also contribute to the creation of solid social networks, which improve the sense of community and well-being.

2.2.3 Demonstrative outcomes of simulation

Baseline - No Coworking. As a first scenario for the simulation, we consider the case in which co-working is not allowed because the necessary infrastructures are missing. In this case we can only measure the reduction of population. Parameters are set as:

- Rate Percentage: 10

- Time simulation: 10000

By running the simulation in a context where no co-working spaces are available, we observe that the average number of inhabitants in the considered valleys slightly decreases, passing from 1450 to 1350. We observe that part of the population tends to move to Aosta or outside the region. Local services earnings will consequently slightly decrease, while workers' satisfaction, CO2 emissions, etc. will not significantly change (reductions being directly associated with population reduction).

Population reduction in remote areas depends on many intertwined factors, among which reduction of traditional activities (like agriculture and rearing), lack of opportunities, like qualified work positions, lack of services/specialists like schools and medical doctors, lack of advanced infrastructures that, in turn, does not allow remote work making, the valleys, on the whole, less attractive. Our simulation does not model the complex dynamics of population reduction per se.

The realization of tools like the simulator described in these pages is a promising direction for providing decision makers the means for foreseeing the impact of the creation of networks of co-working spaces in alpine valleys.

The estimates that were used in the simulation are not related to specific socio-economic models, whose complexity goes beyond the aims of the demonstrator. So, for instance, workers' satisfaction is simply calculated on the basis of the only measures that are computed in the simulation, which are the distance and the economic cost of fuel. In the real world many other factors are involved. Similarly the earnings of the local services are simply associated with the number of people in a valley while actual dynamics would be more complex and variegated. However, the computation concerning the estimate of the number of smart collaborations is, to the best of our knowledge, a first attempt to capture such a number.

We believe that the digitalization of services, by improving access to important resources, reduces the disadvantages of living in a remote area, thus attracting young people more. The improvement of life conditions and the creation of new opportunities fosters local entrepreneurship.

Figure 7. The simulation computed features over time shown by means of charts.

2.3 Strengths and Limits of the Demonstrator

The demonstrator reaches the goal of showing the feasibility of the realization of tools that help foreseeing the impact of a co-working building in a specific geographic area, taking into account information about the population distribution, the characteristics of the population, the local services that are actually present in an area, and also the infrastructures.

Of course, the production of an actual tool would require resources that were not available to this exploration, namely:

1. accurate socio-economic and environment-related models;
2. accurate information sources (e.g. linked open data, statistics, demographics);
3. a design and development team.

All the formulas and assumptions made in the demonstrator were made for the sake of showing the feasibility and the power of such a kind of tool. So, for instance, the percentages of population that are involved (and how) are nothing more than an educated guess. The vehicles' fuel consumption is an estimated average. We used geographic information about actual towns and roads but not of actual local services. We considered roads as infrastructure but not, for instance, high speed internet availability.

The development of actual systems requires a dedicated project. Nevertheless, in the following section we briefly show how mathematical tools, in particular game theory, can come in handy for modeling purposes. Specifically, we will briefly introduce a model that captures the added value (due to smart collaboration) of an NCS.

3. Modeling

We briefly show how it is possible to use mathematical tools to study the catalyst effect of an NCS for what concerns smart collaboration, as well as community well-being and local economy. The model is explained in detail in an article that was published by researchers in NODES (Alderighi et al., 2024). The model is targeted to identify ways in which it is possible to maximize the added value, that is generated by the collaboration itself, by exploiting game theory. In the proposal, the NCS is modeled as a game and the target is to maximize the NCS value. The agents are seen as nodes of the network and they can join/create coalitions to collaborate on specific projects or share resources and knowledge. Each coalition has a weight that, in actual settings, can be determined by features like agents having complementary skills, resources that are shared, networking opportunities.

We denote by N the number of agents. Differently than in the real world this number will not change along the runs. We denote by $S1$ and $S2$ two sets of coalitions. The first contains cooperation coalitions, that is coalitions where agents share a goal, while the latter contains collaboration coalitions, that is coalitions where an agent contributes to another agent's goals. Let $V(S)$ denote the weight of the collaboration/cooperation S . The co-working game is defined by the characteristic function $V: 2^N \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$. In particular, we have that: $V(S1) + V(S2) \leq V(S1 \cup S2)$.

The function is superadditive.

Without getting into the details, it turns out that collaborating in an NCS is more advantageous than acting individually (i.e. the value generated by the collaboration is greater than the sum of the values generated by the individual actions of the agents of the NCS).

Each agent is an operational micro-reality in the NCS. He or she will have an own role and power in the NCS, depending on specific features (e.g. industrial sector, economic-financial weight, kind/level of innovation/technology). In order to understand the power that can potentially be generated by a system that creates an agent network, it is possible to rely on a Shapley Value. Such value helps to evaluate the contribution of each individual in the formation of coalitions. We denote the Shapley Value of agent i as $\phi_i(Val)$, where Val denotes the cumulative value of the agents in a given coalition S . This value quantifies the specific role of each agent in the network and its impact on the overall collaboration. An agent with a high Shapley Value is particularly important for the network, as it makes a significant contribution to collaboration and cooperation.

Once the value of each node has been estimated, it is possible to calculate the total value of the NCS by aggregating the Shapley Values of each node:

$$\phi_{NCS}(Val) = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi S^i(.)$$

where $(.)$ can include parameters related to the characteristic function $V(S)$ that reflect the objectives of the NCS, such as promoting innovation, sharing resources, networking, coalition success and integration of different skills. This allows the calculation to be adapted to the unique characteristics of the network and its nodes.

This suggests that the agents involved should be encouraged to cooperate and adopt collaborative strategies to maximize the benefits for all participants. The Shapley Value can be

helpful in better understanding each agent's role. In conclusion, the model provides a theoretical framework for understanding and promoting collaboration and cooperation within an NCS, highlighting the importance of creating synergies and added value through collaboration between different agents.

Also in this case the mathematical framework is a showcase of the possibilities that are opened by the adoption of formal models on the proof of properties of decision-support systems. An improved model, characterized by the attempt of making a twofold optimization of both the value the NCS can produce and the quality of life of its patrons is currently under development.

3.1 Monitor

The monitoring phase of business process management aims at implementing all the necessary measures to understand whether the real executions of the business processes differ from the designed process model. It may seem strange that a process is performed in reality differently from how it is expected to be executed in theory. However, one should keep in mind that the experts of the process are the workers, more than the managers or the designers, and that the actual environment in which processes are executed may or may not support the expected actions, may or may not offer unforeseen alternatives, may or may not present unforeseen cases. This is particularly true in case of smart collaborations, where individuals who do not have a common background nor share consolidated practices, join forces to pursue a common goal. Smart collaborations, indeed, have an horizontal nature, spanning through many roles and functions, while most business processes are pretty specialized on the activities they organize.

Therefore, it is often the case that workers/collaborators implement shortcuts or workarounds in order to speed up the process or to handle situations that the process model does not foresee. Identifying these differences may support managers in improving the process by implementing actual usage practices as part of the model and, consequently, in modifying the information systems supporting the processes. Additionally, by identifying discrepancies, managers can take countermeasures where the implemented process is not in line with the law or with the internal policies.

On the other hand, also co-working spaces and NCS need to be managed, and their management passes through business processes and can be subject to the same kind of variations, which is equally important to identify.

This section provides a demonstration of a technique called conformance checking, aiming at comparing an actual execution with a process model. We enhanced this technique by modeling and accounting for responsibilities on the way the process is executed. Responsibilities, indeed, are an important part of an organization's management. However, in most of the techniques, they are neglected. We demonstrate how taking them into account improves conformance results. Details can be found in (Baldoni et al, 2024).

3.2 Responsibilities

Responsibilities are often used for capturing task distribution with the expectation that the one who is responsible for a task will perform it at the right moment and with the right means. This is, for instance, the case of RACI matrices, which are indeed used to specify the different kinds of responsibilities that roles have on activities. As another example, in BPMN the specification of the role that is responsible for the execution of a process activity is modeled by means of lanes.

Responsibilities can, however, be more complex. For instance, an activity might be adequately executed only if certain other activities occur, conforming to a given pattern (think of two activities to be performed in sequence because the former provides an input needed by the latter).

More in detail, we specify responsibilities declaratively, allowing one to complement a procedural process model with explicit relationships between activities that are not already captured by the process model itself. Such relationships include, but are not limited to, causal relationships, where an activity produces an outcome that is needed by another. So, for instance, in the case of a sequence of activities, the process model does not necessarily express possible causal dependencies. As a consequence, in order to match an execution with a model, classical approaches find the model paths that match the highest number of activities of the execution sequence. Thus, the case in which neither of two consecutive activities is performed always counts as two mismatches with respect to the model. However, the absence of the second activity might be justified by the lack of proper input given the absence of the first activity.

We assume that the actors, playing roles in a business organization, do act to support the organization in reaching its goals, and hence they behave in accordance with their responsibilities. Under this assumption, we add responsibilities to the model description and we define a cost of alignment which depends both on the number of mismatches, and on respect of the responsibilities that are defined in the model. While neglected responsibilities always amount to costs, mismatches increase the cost only when they are not consistent with some responsibilities. Therefore, responsibilities not only enable a more informed search for an optimal alignment than just the control flow, but also represent a valuable source of information in the aftermath. In fact, the possibility of reasoning on the set of satisfied and neglected responsibilities allows a better understanding of what went wrong in the execution, and possibly pinpoints the root causes. This information could be used to improve the process, for instance, by regimenting some parts of the process or to make it more permissive.

A responsibility relation is formally denoted as

$$R(x, u, v)$$

where x is a role, u is a context condition, and v is the task assigned to x . Intuitively, $R(x, u, v)$ states that any actor playing the role x will be receptive to the request/need of bringing about v if u holds.

Condition u and task v can both be simple activities or temporal patterns of activity executions.

Example (Alignments and Responsibilities). In this example, we consider a process for co-working space reservation. When a reservation is made (Make Reservation – MR), then it can either be paid directly (Payment – P), or a request for remote payment is first sent (Send Payment Request – SPR), then a reservation confirmation upon payment is sent (Send Reservation Notification - SRN). Following this specification, two model runs are possible:

- $E1 = \langle MR, P \rangle$
- $E2 = \langle MR, SPR, SRN \rangle$

Let us consider the observed execution trace: $T = \langle MR \rangle$ that is, only Make Reservation is observed. The possible alignments with trace T are the following, where \gg represents a mismatch (i.e., a move where either the log trace or the model moves one step).

$$A1 = \frac{MR \gg}{MR \quad P}$$

$$A2 = \frac{MR \gg \gg}{MR \quad SPR \quad SRN}$$

Classical approaches conclude that $A1$ is the optimal alignment, having one mismatch only, while $A2$ has two. Therefore, the model execution closer to trace T is $E1$. Let us now assume that the model is complemented with an explicit representation of responsibilities, and that the employee is responsible for sending a Reservation notification only after the Payment Request has been sent and only in case it is sent. Assessing the two alignments against such a responsibility allows us to observe that the lack of Send Reservation Notification (SRN) in $A2$ is justified by the fact that the Payment Request was not sent (for some reason). Therefore, while the absence of Send Payment Request (SPR) is not justified by any responsibility (and thus has to be counted as a mismatch in the alignment), the absence of Send Reservation Notification (SRN) is justified by the non-occurrence of Send Payment Request. As a result, the two alignments can be considered equivalent in terms of the number of mismatches. In other words, the two process executions are equally possible as an alignment of the execution T .

To capture these kinds of conditions in responsibilities, it is possible to rely on several temporal logics. In our proposal, we rely on Precedence Logic (Singh and Huns, 2005) for its simplicity. Precedence logic is an event-based linear temporal logic, obtained from propositional logic augmented with the temporal operator (\cdot) before.

Example (Responsibility). The responsibility mentioned in the previous example can be expressed by $R(E, SRN, SPR \cdot SRN)$ modeling that the employee E is responsible that whenever Send Reservation Notification is performed, it is performed only after Send Payment Request ($SPR \cdot SRN$).

For details on the formalization, please refer to (Baldoni et al., 2024).

3.3 Process Alignment

Process alignment corresponds to comparing a process path against an execution trace (i.e., an actual execution). Generally, the objective is to find, among the possible ones, an alignment that is optimal to a criterion of preference. Intuitively, an alignment proceeds step-by-step on the model and on the execution: at each step, if the activity in the model and the one in the execution match each other, a synchronous move is made, and both model and log advance one step. Otherwise, either the model moves and the log does not, or the other way around, the log moves and the model does not. Usually, to find an optimal matching, a cost function associated with mismatches (i.e., asynchronous moves) is defined. So, an optimal alignment is the one that minimizes the cumulative cost of the mismatches. Among the existing approaches, the classical one is to assign the same cost to each mismatch, so optimality is reached by minimizing the number of asynchronous moves.

In our approach, an optimal alignment is determined by taking into account both the alignment between an execution and a model path and the involved responsibilities. Intuitively, we collect all the responsibilities that are involved in the process, and verify whether they are satisfied during

the execution, or some of the patterns specified by the precedence logic are not satisfied. The cost of an alignment, thus, also takes into account the cost of neglected responsibilities. We also use responsibilities to evaluate whether a model move (i.e., a missing activity on the log side) is justified because the execution of the corresponding activity would violate a responsibility. In this case, we do not consider the mismatch as an error but rather as a proper behavior. In this way, we compute the cost of alignment by summing the number of not-justified mismatches and the responsibilities that are violated by the considered execution. The optimal alignment is the one minimizing such cost.

The algorithm for optimal alignment computation can be found in (Baldoni et al., 2024).

Figure 8: A simplified version of the Reservation Creation Process

3.4 Demonstrative Outcomes of Process Alignments and Responsibilities

As a demonstration of the approach, let us consider a process for the creation of a reservation in a coworking space. The simplified process model is represented in Figure 8. The process starts with the creation of the reservation (Make Reservation - MR) and its memorization into the system (Record Reservation - RR). Of course, this happens upon request by a customer. For the sake of simplicity and synthesis, we omit this part. At this point, the customer has two options: either (s)he decides to pay remotely, thus a notification for remote payment is sent (Send Remote Payment - SRP), or (s)he pays immediately (Payment - P), thus a receipt must be given after (Give Receipt - GR).

Let us now consider an execution where the activities Make Reservation and Record Reservation are observed. Thus, the execution T looks like: $\langle MR, RR \rangle$. This execution does not match one hundred percent with an execution from the model. The process alignment would compare the matches with the two possible executions of the process model, resulting in the following alignments.

$$A1 = \frac{MR \quad RR \quad \gg \quad \gg}{MR \quad RR \quad P \quad GR}$$

$$A2 = \frac{MR \quad RR \quad \gg}{MR \quad RR \quad SRP}$$

According to classical approaches, A2 is to be preferred because it contains one mismatch only, while A1 contains two. However, knowing the semantics of the process, there is no reason to believe that A2 is more likely to have happened with respect to A1. We could indeed believe that

an employee would not provide a receipt unless the payment is received. By means of the responsibilities, we can capture these aspects. Consider the responsibility

$R(E, GR, P \cdot GR)$

It states that the employee has the responsibility that if a Give Receipt (GR) occurs, then this must happen only after the occurrence of Payment (P).

If we evaluate the two alignments with respect to the responsibility, the non-occurrence of GR in A1 is justified by R. Indeed, if the employee performs GR even when not observing P the responsibility would have been violated. This justifies his/her choice of not performing GR. In light of this evaluation, the two alignments are equal, meaning that one cannot say that one path is more likely to correspond to the observed sequence of action than the other.

As one can see by this example, leveraging responsibility allows one to reconstruct what should have happened and potentially to obtain a justification for why a real execution went differently than expected.

3.5 Strengths and Limits of the Demonstrator

The approach has the potential to produce very powerful tools that overcome the limitations of current business process alignment tools by identifying misalignments that take into account the agents' responsibilities. Its limit stands in its TRL: in order to develop such innovative tools, it is necessary to integrate responsibility representation languages, and the algorithms for handling them, into commercial (possibly new) products. This could be done in future projects, as the expected effort is great.

4. Improve

The improve (or enhancement) phase of Business Process Management is closely related to the monitoring phase. Its primary goal is to understand how a process is performed in reality, and investigate the reasons of possible differences with respect to what expected, in order to improve it.

In order to provide a demonstration of techniques that can be applied in the monitoring phase, we described how traditional conformance checking and conformance checking enhanced with responsibilities work. These techniques allow one to identify where a process model and a real execution differ. However, the identification of possible improvements requires an analysis performed by domain experts, as this goes beyond what can be achieved by applying an automated system alone.

Opportunities for improvement are typically identified through the organization's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). For example, depending on organizational priorities, improvement may focus on reducing costs, maximizing resource utilization, minimizing bottlenecks, or enhancing customer satisfaction.

To this aim, we show the adoption of business process management and process mining techniques to support the process analysis performed by a domain expert. We demonstrate its adoption by describing the collaboration that has been performed as part of the project with an

IT company in the territory. We summarize here the main steps performed and the main findings. The demonstrator has already been presented in the September 2024 Deliverable 8 (Transparent Processes for Smart Work in the Mountain Reality). For completeness, we summarize the main aspects in this section.

The collaboration with the company developed through the following steps:

1. We modelled the company's model using the standard notation BPMN. This ensures that the language used for the model representation contains all the necessary constructs to represent the process in a detailed and not ambiguous way.
2. Then we analysed the developed process model with the company.
3. We acquired and analysed real data on the execution of the process, to obtain information about the actual executions compared with the theoretical model developed.

From this collaboration with the company, we elaborated a set of guidelines consisting of few steps to support small and medium-size companies and organizations in the applying process mining. These results are reported in (Deliverable 5) and summarized in this section for simplicity.

4.1 The process model

The company involved in the project is working in the ICT sector and consists of three branches. The main services it offers include the design and implementation of solutions for Enterprise Networking, Cyber Security, Internet of Things, Data Center & Cloud and Digital Workplace; proactive management of the infrastructure, of cyber-security, of application performance; training for ICT professionals.

The company was interested in analysing the ticket management process, particularly in the subprocess handling customer service requests (Request Fulfillment Process). The company had an existing process model that used a combination of graphical and textual representations. The service is typically delivered remotely, with technicians connecting to the client's systems via VPN or desktop conferencing tools. Once a service request is received through email, phone, or a self-service portal, the company uses its system to assign tasks, manage communications, and ensure timely resolution. Technicians document all actions within the system until the request is resolved and the case is closed.

While the company's original process model is detailed, it lacks clarity and comprehensiveness. The graphical representation provided by the company misses

- alternative execution paths,
- critical decision points, and
- conditional flows.

The textual descriptions also failed to provide sufficient detail on certain activities, leading to process ambiguities.

To address these issues, as part of the collaboration within the project, we proposed a redesigned model using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN). BPMN is a standard for representing business processes with well-defined symbols, making processes more transparent and easier to analyze. The new model is more structured and includes:

- **Client Interaction:** Explicit representation of client interaction, with decision points that guide the process flow.
- **Process Activities:** Activities like identifying the client, assigning a ticket, and classifying the request based on priority and type are made clearer.
- **Parallel Activities:** Decision points and parallel gateways were introduced to show processes that could occur concurrently (e.g., classifying the request type and checking contract validity).
- **In-depth Analysis of Requests:** The subprocess for investigating requests is now well-defined, showing how technicians may need to clarify details with clients or consult specialists.

Additionally, activities were better structured into activities and subprocesses.

4.2 Model Evaluation

The redesigned BPMN model was presented to the company for feedback. Several key points emerged during this evaluation:

Level of Detail. Some activities in the original model were either overly simplistic or too detailed. For example, tasks like "assign technician" were underspecified, while others, like "change ticket state," were atomic (one-step) activities. The company was advised to standardize these activities, breaking down complex tasks into more manageable steps and providing clearer definitions for ambiguous tasks.

Missing Activities. A major gap identified in the original model was that some information was not explicit in the model, but rather it was kept among the workers or domain expert. For instance, the model was lacking the activities concerning the handling of request escalation between technicians. The BPMN model incorporates this missing element, clarifying the process flow.

Missing Alternatives. Certain decision points were found to be incomplete. For example, the model did not clearly define what happens if a problem cannot be solved remotely or if a client is dissatisfied with the solution. The new BPMN model highlights all possible alternatives and ensures that each path leading to problem resolution is represented.

4.3 Analysis by way of Process Mining

Process mining techniques were applied to analyze real data from the company's ticket management system, aiming to uncover how processes are executed in practice rather than how they are ideally supposed to run. This analysis leveraged data from the company's databases, specifically logs detailing how tickets are handled from creation to closure. These logs reveal both the structured aspects of ticket management and the hidden shortcuts workers may take to improve efficiency.

4.3.1 Data Overview

The company provided an Excel file containing three primary data sheets:

- General ticket information: Basic details of the tickets.
- State changes: Captures transitions between ticket states (i.e., the status in which a ticket can be, such as open, resolved and so on).
- Operations performed: Detailed actions on each ticket.

The dataset contains records for 4.202 tickets from a specified period, with a total of 17.848 records detailing state changes and operations.

4.3.2 Analysis Methodology

The company's previous approach to analyzing processes relied mainly on ad-hoc SQL queries, which did not provide a comprehensive or step-by-step view of ticket handling. Process mining, by contrast, offers a more structured and visual way of understanding ticket management.

The process mining methodology followed several steps:

1. Data Gathering: The data was extracted and structured for analysis.
2. Data Semantics: Understanding the meaning behind each field in the dataset, including how ticket statuses and actions relate to the overall workflow.
3. Informal Communications: Discussions with employees revealed informal practices, such as using the "In Progress" state in ways not officially documented, to simplify workflow.
4. Query Identification: The company, alongside the academic team, identified key aspects of ticket management that needed investigation. These include analyzing anomalous behaviors like tickets that take too long or deviate from the expected flow.
5. Process Visualization: The process was then visualized using process mining tools like DISCO (Fluxicon Disco), which helped generate a process map representing how tickets actually flowed through the system (see Figure 9). This visualization made it easier to detect inefficiencies or inconsistencies in the process.

Figure 9. Process Map generated with DISCO by applying process discovery techniques

The analysis revealed a few critical aspects.

Anomalies in Ticket Handling. Certain tickets exhibited unusual patterns, such as bypassing specific states or taking longer than expected at certain stages. These anomalies could point to inefficiencies or gaps in the current system.

Shortcuts and Workarounds. Workers were found to take shortcuts, like skipping certain steps in the process when the system didn't support them well enough. While this helped speed up ticket resolution, it also highlighted the need for system improvements.

For instance, each ticket goes through various states, such as Open, In Progress, Customer Action, Partner Action, Solution Proposed, Resolved, and Closed. Ideally, tickets follow a well-defined flow through these states, but workers admit to bypass or accelerate certain steps due to system limitations or personal preferences. Taking into account these aspects can be valuable for process improvement.

Process Improvement. The process mining analysis pointed to several areas where the company could streamline its workflow. By mapping the actual process steps and comparing them to the

ideal flow, the company could identify where employees were deviating from the prescribed process and why.

4.4 Process Mining Application: a set of Guidelines

Several companies offering support for process mining application exists. However, the cost for such services is accessible for big companies only. In this section we provide a few guidelines aiming at assisting small and medium-sized companies and organization in taking advantage of process mining. However, we are aware that the task remains challenging.

Step 1 - Objectives and Data

- Define the objective of the analysis (business goal).
- Understand what data is available, what it represents, and how it can be integrated if multiple sources are used.

Step 2 - Process

- Identify the process to analyse (better to focus one process at a time)

Step 3 - Interest

- Identify a set of questions the company wants to answer
- Prioritize the questions in an ordered list

Step 4 - Data preparation

- Select and prepare the data
- Make sure the data is consistent and assess the level of completeness
- If possible, fill the gaps by integrating with additional data sources

Step 5 - Tools

- Identify which tools are suitable for answering the identified questions
- Apply the tools to the data
- Check which questions can be answered and which not

Step 6 - Include the experts

- Analyse the results with the experts as soon as possible

Step 7 - Iterate

- Concrete answer to the questions may indicate that the questions were not well formulated or were imprecise. New questions may be triggered by the analysis, as well as interpretations of the results.
- Formulate new questions or refine the existing and repeat the analysis process

4.5 Strengths and Limits of the Demonstrator

The approach and the methodology are very powerful and proved effective in a real-world scenario. The limit, in this case, stands in the lack of a process-oriented mentality in companies. Sometimes such a lack is fostered by the adoption of tools that, for meeting the needs of many realities, provide loose constraints on the contexts when things should be done. People adapt and invent (sometimes individual) ways/practices for adding the meanings that the tool does not incorporate. The education to a process-oriented mind is the actual effort.

5. Conclusions

In this deliverable we reported on a number of tools that can serve the goal of contrasting depopulation in the mountain regions, and that can easily be applied to other geographic areas of interest. Our claim is that depopulation can be contrasted by fostering social innovation, and in particular by supporting the creation of smart collaborations in a broad sense, that is, both within a company and across companies with the help of technology. This is a complex goal, that requires the interplay of economic, social, and environmental actions. We have focussed on the impact of networks of co-working spaces, which can serve a wide range of purposes, and displayed a showcase of demonstrators that can support decision makers, politicians, and also companies in deciding about possible investments because they allow estimating the impact.

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Deliverable 5 - Best practices: Guidelines on: organisational change; firm performance; workers' wellbeing; tools and devices; and digital compliance. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/14012280>
[Autori: UniVda; UniTo; PoliTo; UniBas; LINKS]